

Knocking-out the brassinosteroid-biosynthesis genes *DWARF1* or *DWARF4* produces upright canopy architecture in wheat

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Additional file 1

Figure S1: *DWF1* and *DWF4* homoeologues and mutant alleles used in this study.

Figure S2: Phenotypic characterization of all combinatorial *dwf1* and *dwf4* mutants under glasshouse conditions.

Figure S3: Phenotype of Cadenza and *dwf1-abd* mutant at the tillering stage in the field.

Figure S4: High throughput phenotyping of *dwf1-abd* mutant under Field Scanalyzer.

Figure S5: Expression of *DWF1* genes in wheat variety 'Azhurnaya'.

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Table S1: Homoeologue-specific primers designed to amplify fragments around the deleterious mutations in *TaDWF1* and *TaDWF4* genes.

Table S2: KASP primers designed to differentiate the mutant and wild type allele in segregating *DWF1* and *DWF4* populations.

Table S3: BR levels (pg/mg DW) in *dwf1-abd* and *dwf4-abd* mutants and controls.

Figure S1: *DWF1* and *DWF4* homoeologues and mutant alleles used in this study. (A) *TaDWF1* gene indicating the position of nonsense mutations in the three homoeologues (red arrows) (B) Structure of the *TaDWF1* protein showing conserved domains and the predicted *TaDWF1* proteins encoded by the mutant alleles. (C) *TaDWF4* gene indicating the position of nonsense mutations in the three homoeologues (red arrows) (D) Structure of the *TaDWF4* protein showing conserved domains and the predicted *TaDWF4* proteins encoded by the mutant alleles. Position of nonsense mutations identified from the Cadenza TILLING population are indicated. * = stop codon. Produced using Biorender.com.

Figure S2: Phenotypic characterization of all combinatorial *dwf1* and *dwf4* mutants under glasshouse conditions. (A) Flag Leaf Angle (FLA) at 22 days post anthesis and (B) Final plant height of *tadwf1* combinatorial mutants along with Cadenza (n = 4). (C) FLA at anthesis and (D) Final plant height of *tadwf4* combinatorial mutants along with Cadenza (n = 4). Different letters indicate significant differences between genotypes (obtained from Fisher's unprotected LSD test).

Figure S3: Phenotype of Cadenza and *dwf1-abd* mutant at the tillering stage in the field. The images show 1 m² plots of Cadenza and the *dwf1-abd* mutant at the tillering stage (GS25). The row to row and plant to plant spacing was the same in each plot.

Figure S4: High throughput phenotyping of the *dwf1-abd* mutant under the Field Scanalyzer.

RGB images of *dwf1-abd* (A) and Cadenza (B) at GS69 under the Field Scanalyzer during 2020-21. The left panel shows the original image and the right panel shows the segmented RGB image. RGB images showing highlighted spikes in red in *dwf1-abd* (C) and Cadenza (D) at GS69. These images were used to estimate spike density (number of spikes/m²).

Figure S5: Expression of *DWF1* in wheat cultivar 'Azhurnaya'. The organ expression profile is shown as transcripts per million (TPM) for the *TaDWF1* homoeologues. The data were obtained from <https://www.wheat-expression.com/>.

Table S1: Homoeologue-specific primers designed to amplify fragments around the deleterious mutations in *DWF1* and *DWF4*.

The primer sequences, fragment lengths and Tm (°C) are listed.

Gene	Forward primer (5' - 3')	Reverse primer (5' - 3')	Amplicon length (bp)	Tm (°C)
<i>DWF1-A</i>	ATGTGGTCCGCCATGAAGTCC	TCGACCTCGAAGTGCCTGACG	188	66
<i>DWF1-B</i>	TCAGCTAACATCTCTTTGTACA	TCACGACCTTCTGCACGTTC	265	60
<i>DWF1-D</i>	TCAGCTAACATCTCTTTGTACT	TGGGGATGAGCTTGATCTCA	745	60
<i>DWF4-A</i>	TCAGTACAGGCATGCGAGCAG	CGCGGACACCACCCCTTCAT	660	66
<i>DWF4-B</i>	TCTCTCTCTCTCCAACCCATCATC	CGCATGCCTGTACTGATGTATA	403	62
<i>DWF4-D</i>	GATCTGTGCTAAACTAGACT	ACGCATATATCTTGCACTGAT	293	62

Commented [SP1]: I updated this table to be consistent with our other tables, removed chromosome column, added bp units etc.

Table S2: KASP primers designed to differentiate between the mutant and wild-type alleles in segregating *DWF1* and *DWF4* populations. Tail sequences GAAGGTGACCAAGTTCATGCT (FAM) and GAAGGTGCGGAGTCAACGGATT (HEX) were added to the 5' end of the forward primers to differentiate mutant (MT) and wild-type (WT) alleles, respectively. The nucleotide distinguishing wild-type and mutant alleles is in bold.

Gene	Forward Primer (5' - 3') (MT)	Forward Primer (5' - 3') (WT)	Common primer (5' -3')
<i>DWF1-A</i>	CACGTTGCGCATGCCGACGGCGAT T	CACGTTGCGCATGCCGACGGCGAT C	ACCCAAGAAGGACGGCCTC
<i>DWF1-B</i>	ACGAGGATCCATCGGAACT A	ACGAGGATCCATCGGAACT G	CGACCAAAGAGGAAGAAGGTC
<i>DWF1-D</i>	GGAACCCGAGAGTGCCCT A	GGAACCCGAGAGTGCCCT G	CGAGTACTCCGACCTCTTCTA
<i>DWF4-A</i>	GGCGGCATCCTTGCAA A T A	GGCGGCATCCTTGCAA A T G	CTGAGGAAGTTGAGGGAGATGG
<i>DWF4-B</i>	TTCGTCCGGCCGCTCCACT T	TTCGTCCGGCCGCTCCACC	CATCCTCCTGGCCCTGCTCA
<i>DWF4-D</i>	AACCATCTCTTTGTAGTCTTCT	AACCATCTCTTTGTAGTCTTCC	ATGGAAATATTGACAGTGAATCCA

Table S3: BR levels (pg/mg DW) in *dwf1-abd* and *dwf4-abd* mutants and controls. Mean values (pg/mg DW) \pm SD are shown for the *dwf1-abd* and *dwf4-abd* mutants along with the *DWF1-NS*, *DWF4-NS* and Cadenza controls at the seedling stage. The data were analysed using one-way ANOVA which yielded *p*-values, SED, and LSD at 5% level of significance. Fisher's unprotectd LSD test was performed for multiple pair-wise comparisons. *P* values *0.05>*P*>0.01, **0.01>*P*>0.001, ***0.0001>*P*>0.00001 (obtained from Fisher's unprotectd test)

		<i>dwf1-abd</i>	<i>DWF1-NS</i>	<i>dwf4-abd</i>	<i>DWF4-NS</i>	Cadenza	<i>p</i> -value	SED	LSD at 5%
BR content (pg/mg DW)	CR	6.23 \pm 0.43****	759.05 \pm 67.02	721.78 \pm 61.77*	811.45 \pm 21.46	603.61 \pm 55.63	<.001	42.165	89.872
	CN	1.27 \pm 0.34****	16.56 \pm 0.78	18.99 \pm 0.81	19.28 \pm 0.94	17.51 \pm 1.84	<.001	0.868	1.85
	6-oxoCN	0.22 \pm 0.03***	0.82 \pm 0.12	0.72 \pm 0.12	0.78 \pm 0.19	0.79 \pm 0.17	<.001	0.112	0.239
	6-deoxoCT	4.11 \pm 0.43*	4.71 \pm 0.33	4.81 \pm 0.12****	3.19 \pm 0.47	3.46 \pm 0.10	<.001	0.27	0.575
	6-deoxoTY	40.00 \pm 5.20	33.41 \pm 1.98	36.24 \pm 3.80****	16.09 \pm 1.45	38.88 \pm 5.57	<.001	3.238	6.903
	TY	0.0002 \pm 0.0001**	0.0004 \pm 0.0001	0.0005 \pm 0.0000	0.0005 \pm 0.0002	0.0006 \pm 0.0001	0.002	0.000078	0.00016
	CS	0.0015 \pm 0.0008**	0.0005 \pm 0.0001	0.0010 \pm 0.0002	0.0003 \pm 0.0001	0.0008 \pm 0.0003	0.015	0.00031	0.00067
	BL	0.021 \pm 0.003****	0.006 \pm 0.003	0.017 \pm 0.003**	0.009 \pm 0.002	0.014 \pm 0.002	<.001	0.0025	0.0054
	DS	0.0015 \pm 0.0006	0.0009 \pm 0.001	0.0004 \pm 0.0003	0.0006 \pm 0.0004	0.0004 \pm 0.0002	0.018	0.0003	0.0006